

are also due to U. G. C., New Delhi for financial assistance.

References

1. S. S. TIWARI and R. K. SATSANGI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, **56**, 627.
2. V. K. SRIVASTAVA, B. R. PANDEY, R. C. GUPTA, J. P. BARTHWAJ and K. KISHORR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, **56**, 1024.

Synthesis of 4-N-Benzyl-N-cyanoethylamino-2-methyl-benzylidene aniline and Its Reaction with Hydrazine, 2 : 4-Dinitrophenylhydrazine, Carboxylic Acid Hydrazides and Ethylmalonate

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Manuscript received 4 March 1980, revised 8 September 1980, accepted 29 October 1980

PHENYLIMINO group in Schiff's bases could be replaced by phenylhydrazine, 2 : 4-dinitrophenylhydrazine¹, and aromatic benzoic acid hydrazides². It was therefore thought worthwhile to see whether this group is also subject to displacement by hydrazine and ethylmalonate. In this note the reactions of hydrazine, 2 : 4-dinitrophenylhydrazine, carboxylic acid hydrazides and ethylmalonate with 4-N-benzyl-N-cyanoethylamino-2-methyl-benzylidene aniline are described. In each case it has been observed that the phenylimino group in(I) has been replaced by azine, 2 : 4-dinitrophenylhydrazono, benzoylhydrazono and ethyl-malonate groups to give II, III, IV and V respectively. Direct condensation of 4-N-benzyl-N-cyanoethylamino-2-methyl benzaldehyde³ with hydrazine, 2 : 4-dinitrophenylhydrazine, hydrazides and malonic-ester also furnished II, III, IV and V respectively. The identities of II, III, IV and V prepared by the above methods were established by means of elemental analysis, m.p., m.m.p. and superimposable i.r. spectra.

I R = -CH = NC₆H₅

(II)

III R = -CH = NNH-C₆H₃(NO₂)₂

IV R = -CH = NNH-CO-C₆H₄(R₁)

(R₁ = H, 2-CH₃, 2-Cl, 3-CH₃, 3-NO₂, 4-NO₂, 4-Cl)

V R = -CH = C(CO₂Et)₂

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillary and are uncorrected.

4-N-Benzyl-N-cyanoethylamino-2-methylbenzylidene-aniline(I) :

4-N-Benzyl-N-cyanoethylamino-2-methylbenzaldehyde (0.01 mol.), aniline (0.01 mol.) and four drops of piperidine were taken in a round bottomed flask and the mixture heated in an oil bath for 5 hours at 100-105°. The product obtained was recrystallised from aq. ethanol, m.p., 97°, (yield, 54%) (Found : C, 81.92 ; H, 6.73 ; N, 11.44%. C₂₄H₂₃N₃ requires C, 81.58 ; H, 6.52 ; N, 11.9%)

N'-N''-Bis-(N-benzyl-N-cyanoethylamino-2-methylbenzylidene)-hydrazine(II) :

Method-A :

4-N-Benzyl-N-cyanoethylamino-2-methyl benzaldehyde (0.001 mol), hydrazine hydrate (0.003 mol, 80%), glacial acetic acid (2 ml) and ethanol (4 ml) were refluxed for half an hour. The product obtained was recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 157°, (yield, 85%). (Found : C, 77.91 ; H, 6.41 ; N, 14.86%. C₃₆H₃₆N₆ requires C, 78.26 ; H, 6.52 ; N, 15.22%).

Method-B :

Schiff's base (0.001 mol), hydrazine hydrate (0.003 mol, 80%), glacial acetic acid (2 ml) and ethanol (4 ml) were refluxed for an hour. The product obtained was recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 157° (yield, 90.6%).

N'-(2 : 4-Dinitrophenyl)-N''-4-(N-benzyl-N-cyanoethylamino-2-methylbenzylidene)-hydrazine(III) :

Method-A :

To an alcoholic solution of 4-N-benzyl-N-cyanoethylamino-2-methyl benzaldehyde (0.001 mol.), 2 : 4-dinitrophenylhydrazine (0.001 mol.) was added. The contents were heated for 20 minutes and kept for some time. The dark brown crystals separated were washed with hot ethanol, m.p. 229° (yield, 97.3%). (Found : C, 62.36 ; H, 4.56 ; N, 18.59%. C₂₄H₂₂N₆O₄ requires C, 62.88 ; H, 4.80 ; N, 18.34%).

Method-B :

To an alcoholic solution of the Schiff's base (0.001 mol.), 2 : 4-dinitrophenylhydrazine (0.001 mol.) was added. The contents were heated for 20 minutes and kept for some time. The dark brown crystals separated were washed with hot ethanol, m.p. 229°, (yield, 87%).

TABLE 1—N'-(R-BENZOYL)-N''-(4-N-BENZYL-N-CYANOETHYLAMINO-2-METHYL BENZYLIDENE)-HYDRAZINE(IV)

No.	R	m.p. (°C)	Yield% from aldehyde	Yield% from I	Molecular Formula	Found	% N* Required
1.	H	168	88.1	74	C ₂₅ H ₂₄ N ₄ O	13.79	14.14
2.	3-NO ₂	126	75.0	54	C ₂₅ H ₂₃ N ₄ O ₃	15.77	15.87
3.	4-NO ₂	202	83.3	68	C ₂₅ H ₂₃ N ₄ O ₃	15.56	15.87
4.	2-Cl	143	84.0	34	C ₂₅ H ₂₃ N ₄ OCl	13.29	13.01
5.	4-Cl	164	59.9	72	C ₂₅ H ₂₃ N ₄ OCl	12.83	13.01
6.	2-CH ₃	138	61.0	44	C ₂₆ H ₂₆ N ₄ O	13.52	13.66
7.	3-CH ₃	140	63.3	57	C ₂₆ H ₂₆ N ₄ O	13.95	13.66

* All compounds gave satisfactory C and H analysis.

N'-(Benzoyl)-N''-(4-N-benzyl-N-cyanoethylamino-2-methyl-benzylidene)-hydrazine(IV) :

Method-A :

4-N-Benzyl-N-cyanoethylamino-2-methyl benzaldehyde (0.001 mol), was dissolved in 10 ml of boiling ethanol. Benzoic acid hydrazide (0.001 mol) was added to it in small portions with shaking. The reaction mixture was refluxed for two hours. The product thus separated was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol.

Method-B :

Schiff's base (0.001 mol) and benzoic acid hydrazide (0.001 mol) were suspended in ethanol (10 ml) containing two drops of acetic acid. The reaction mixture was heated under reflux for two hours, cooled and filtered. The product recrystallised from ethanol.

All the seven compounds listed in Table 1 were prepared by both the methods. Their i.r. spectra were perfectly superimposed.

4-N-Benzyl-N-cyanoethylamino-2-methyl-benzylidene diethylmalonate(V) :

Method-A :

4-N-Benzyl-N-cyanoethylamino-2-methyl benzaldehyde (0.001 mol), diethylmalonate (0.001 mol) and four drops of piperidine were taken in a round bottomed flask and the mixture heated in an oil bath for 5 hours at 100-105°. The product obtained was recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 124° (yield, 51.8%). (Found : C, 70.58 ; H, 6.92 ; N, 6.74%. C₂₅H₂₈N₂O₄ requires C, 71.43 ; H, 6.67 ; N, 6.67%).

Method-B :

Schiff's base (0.001 mol), diethylmalonate (0.001 mol) and four drops of piperidine were taken in a round bottomed flask and the mixture heated in an oil bath for 5 hours at 100-105°. The

product obtained was recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 124° (yield, 38%).

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the C.S.I.R. for the award of a Junior Research Fellowship to one of them (A. K. D.).

References

1. N. S. KOZLOV, V. D. PAK, M. M. LUK'YANOVA, E. A. BRITAN and Z. A. ABRAMOVA, *Tr. Perm. Selkhoz. Inst., U.S.S.R.*, 1970, 68, 101, From Ref. *Zh. Khim.*, 1971, Atstr. No. 12zh, 246.
2. RAJENDRA S. VARMA. *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, 55, 1052.
3. I. M. HORA, (Private Communication).

Synthesis of Chalcones from 2-Hydroxy-3-Bromo-4-*n*-Propoxy-5-Nitroacetophenone as Antibacterial Agents

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Manuscript received 4 December 1979, revised 30 September 1980,
accepted 28 January 1981

THE germicidal, bactericidal, fungicidal and carcinogenic action of chalcones and analogous compounds have been reported by various workers¹⁻¹¹. Wilson and coworkers¹² observed that methoxy and hydroxy chalcones can check up the destruction of adrenaline. The present investigation is an attempt to synthesise chalcones having bromo and nitro groups and to study their antibacterial activity against positive bacteria (*S.aureus*) and gram negative bacteria (*E.coli*).